

Demystifying of Multimodal Framework for Outcome-Based Education and Student-Centered Learning Approach for Sustainable Education

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Abstract—The global educational landscape currently has a lot of promise for Outcome-Based Education (OBE). At the policy level of the NEP-2020, adopting OBE and student-centered learning has also received priority in recent years. The current study's objective was to demystify the multimodal framework for this new-age education employing Indian faculties on the country's recent paradigm shift in education. The researcher used a questionnaire that received 280 responses from faculties and a few professors in outcome-based education from higher education institutions. The quantitative data show that teachers have positive views toward NEP education. The findings also indicate a direct and positive association between knowledge, beliefs, trust, willingness, and acceptance of OBE. The integrated model also established the mediating role of OBE between selected manifest and sustainable education. The findings will assist the NEP-MHRD in creating appropriate policies and emphasizing the current paradigm shift in the future while resolving the major issues to ensure the implementation's effectiveness. A broad understanding of OBE and new-age learning would benefit faculties engaging in higher education.

Keywords—Sustainable Education (SE), Outcome-Based Education (OBE), Higher Education Institutions (HEI), Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).

I. INTRODUCTION

It is necessary to promote sustainability if the world is to overcome its environmental and social difficulties, such as climate change, environmental degradation, conflict and injustice, poverty, and education [1]. There are lots of ways to enhance and nurture the output of education. The buzzword 'Sustainable Education, also known as education for sustainable development (ESD), is an approach to education that advances the principles and practices of sustainability. It aims to develop knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that empower individuals to contribute to an environmentally and socially sustainable future. Sustainable education goes beyond traditional academic subjects and incorporates environmental stewardship, social equity, economic prosperity, and cultural diversity. It seeks to foster a deep understanding of the interconnections between environmental, social, and economic systems [2–4].

Outcome-Based Education (OBE) is an educational methodology that defines desired outcomes or competencies and designs learning experiences to achieve those outcomes. While OBE has been implemented in various disciplines, including world literature, it offers several benefits in the post-pandemic context [5]. The earlier research in higher education

has been greeted as a promoter for teachers to reconsider, recuperate, reframe, and perhaps recalibrate how superlative to serve the people and planet by nurturing greater concern and association. OBE is an educational philosophy and approach that defines clear and measurable student learning outcomes. Instead of solely emphasizing content coverage or instructional methods, OBE emphasizes what students should be able to do or demonstrate because of their educational experiences. In outcome-based education, the desired learning outcomes are typically identified at the beginning of the instructional process. These outcomes can be specific knowledge, skills, or competencies that students are expected to acquire by the end of a course, program, or educational level [6]. The outcomes are often expressed as measurable statements to ensure clarity and assessment. Even so, there hasn't always been enough knowledge to support HEI in planning and developing OBE. Consequently, there have been imperative demands for more research to assist HEI in maximizing their favorable environmental and social impacts through efficient experiential-based programs that hasten the required behavioral changes among key stakeholders, including governments, organizations, communities, and individuals.

II. OVERVIEW OF NEP-2020

The NEP-2020 is a comprehensive framework for the enhancement of education in India. It was approved by the Government of India in July 2020, marking a significant reform in the country's education system. The NEP-2020 aims to delineate the challenges and shortcomings of the previous education policy and provide a more holistic and flexible approach to learning. Some key highlights and objectives of NEP-2020: (i) shifting from a content-centric approach to a more holistic and multidisciplinary education system. It promotes the integration of different subjects and the development of critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills among students, (ii) emphasizing a learner-centered approach to curriculum design and pedagogy. It encourages experiential learning, critical thinking, and skill-based education, moving away from rote memorization and examination-based assessment. (iii) The policy acknowledges the role of technology in education and emphasizes the integration of technology in teaching, learning, and assessment processes. It promotes the use of digital resources, e-learning platforms, and educational technology tools to enhance accessibility and quality of education; (iv) emphasizes the importance of research and innovation in education and aims to create an ecosystem that promotes

research culture, fosters innovation, and encourages collaboration between academia and industry [7]. The policy envisions a transformative and future-oriented education system in India. Its implementation requires collaborative efforts from various stakeholders, including government bodies, educational institutions, teachers, students, and communities, to bring about meaningful changes in the country's education landscape. The current study identifies the current classroom methods in the universities of India within the argument. It also examines the attitudes of Indian faculties and the perspectives of OBE specialists regarding the new educational system. The study is necessary because the national education policy (NEP) has recently shifted from outcome-based to content-based education, and Indian policymakers, curriculum developers, educators, and staff need to be aware of all the potential obstacles that could prevent OBE from being implemented successfully [8]. They should also keep in mind any helpful recommendations for adapting all the key steps in using OBE. Additionally, one of the difficulties that will complicate the method's proper implementation is the lecturers' perspectives. The fundamental shift in teaching and learning activities will result from the fact that the new system will put more emphasis on student participation than teacher engagement, which means that teachers will need to be prepared for this new shift in NEP-2020. Therefore, comprehension of student-centric learning, knowledge, and adjustment on the part of teachers will aid in the successful implementation of OBE-NEP and the areas in which they must be familiar with the phenomena. This study investigates this recent educational trend of NEP and seeks answers to the following research questions:

RQ.1: How do teachers at HEIs perceive new-age learning of NEP-2020?

RQ.2: How does NEP embrace OBE and new-age learning of NEP-2020?

RQ.3: What are new-age outcome-based learning and student-centered education challenges?

To identify knowledge gaps and prospective frameworks for guiding the design of OBE, the sustainability views of Higher Education (HE) were compared to published literature and sustainability models. In this regard, the next section offers an overview of the literature on outcome-based learning. The research methodology used is described in the next parts. Data analysis and interpretation are elucidated in the second last part of the paper. Eventually, discussion, limitations, future scope, and conclusions are outlined.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Research on the factors influencing OBE attitudes and behaviors has increased as public awareness of the global sustainability challenge has increased. Numerous research studies have been conducted in the recent past emphasizing the need for OBE and sustainability to achieve the 17-UN SDGs. [9] established relationship between sustainable education (SE) and the five-pillar sustainability model. They examined students' perceptions of global sustainability by employing quantitative and qualitative analysis in one of the leading business schools in Australia. Recent papers have demonstrated the vital link between HEIs and outcome-based learning and found that sustainability education has grown to be widely acknowledged as a significant factor in developing more virtuous global citizens [10-12].

According to some prominent and advanced research, HEI should actively promote sustainability through outcome-based education programs. To align with the above thought, [11] assessed that higher education is often seen as OBE for imparting capabilities in engineering and management courses. According to the recent Principles of Management Education initiative [5], it has made it easier for technical education worldwide to include OBE in their curricula. As a result, studies on higher engineering have significantly increased recently. According to [12], OBE clearly defines what students are expected to learn. This involves identifying specific, measurable, attainable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) learning outcomes. In the words of [6] and [13], OBE places the student at the center of the educational process. It aims to cater to individual student needs, interests, and abilities, allowing personalized learning experiences. [14-16] stated that OBE focused on developing and accessing competencies rather than just imparting knowledge. Competencies include knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable students to apply what they have learned in real-world contexts. [17] concluded that OBE encourages a cyclical instructional design, assessment, and evaluation process. Educators regularly review and modify their teaching methods and curriculum to enhance student learning and outcomes.

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

A mixed-method technique was used in this research study to gather both numerical data. According to [18], learning more about teachers' views towards implementing OBE models in their classrooms is suggested in light of the research dilemma that emerges when employing traditional teaching and learning techniques in the current environment. The researcher instituted gathering quantitative data by sending a Google Form to 280 respondents during April-June 2023 who were faculties in private universities of Rajasthan. The snowball sampling method was utilized to obtain the quantitative data, and teachers from various organizations were asked to send and share the questionnaire with their colleagues [12]. A pilot survey of 50 respondents was conducted to measure the reliability of the questionnaire, and certain questions were reframed with the help of OBE experts of HEIs to enhance the description of the variables and their standard definitions. This qualitative aspect is necessary to standardize the final questionnaire of the study. A total number of manifests were divided into dependent and independent aspects of the OBE in which teachers' attitudes regarding knowledge, trust, beliefs, willingness, and acceptance of OBE to achieve sustainable education in the backdrop of NEP-2020.

V. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

As advised in most current literature, the approximate sample size was determined using G-power analysis. According to [10], the study's model comprises five predictors for trust, a small effect size of 0.06, and a power requirement of 0.95. The G-Power study revealed that 280 samples are the bare minimum needed. This study had 35% female respondents and 65% male respondents. According to respondents' educational backgrounds, 18% were from social science, 42% were from commerce and management, 28% were from basic science, and 12% were from medical and nursing. 36% of the faculty had experience below 5 years, 48% were between 5-10 years, and the remaining 16% of teachers were above 10 years of experience. Further, most teachers were aware of NEP-2020 and OBE and their

implications. Each manifest is scaled and evaluated on a five-point Likert scale. SEM is a powerful statistical technique that enables researchers to examine complex relationships, test hypotheses, and validate theoretical models by integrating measurement and structural components in a single framework.

Fig. 1. SEM Conceptual Framework for SE-OBE

A. Measurement Model

The measurement model delineates the links between the latent variables and their observed indicators. It describes how the observed variables contribute to the measurement of the latent variables. Factor loadings, which represent the strength and direction of the relationships, are estimated in the measurement model. Table I delineated measurement model assessment findings, reliability, and validity criterion. Cronbach's- α and rho_A are reliability coefficients used to assess the internal consistency of a set of observed variables that measure a latent construct. All constructs met the criteria, with composite reliability (CR) above 0.7 and AVEs above 0.5. [14] states that outer loading larger than 0.5 indicates a satisfactory measurement of the latent construct. Moreover, [14-16] advised always removing exterior loadings below 0.5 from the construction. They emphasized that outer loadings between 0.5 and 0.6 can only be eliminated if eliminating the indication increases composite reliability (CR) and average variance extracted (AVE) above the acceptable range. Keep loadings above 0.7.

TABLE I. RELIABILITY AND VALIDITY CRITERION

Scale	Ch. α	rho_A	CR	AVE	MSV
Knowledge	0.821	0.532	0.560	0.552	0.565

Beliefs	0.871	0.521	0.625	0.420	0.506
Trust	0.714	0.508	0.506	0.450	0.659
Willingness	0.779	0.521	0.662	0.511	0.458
Sustainable Education	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
Acceptance of OBE	0.788	0.520	0.504	0.425	0.422

B. Structural Model

The structural model focuses on the relationships between the latent variables themselves. It specifies the causal or directional relationships between the latent variables in the model. The structural model consists of paths or arrows representing the hypothesized relationships between the latent variables, typically based on theoretical or conceptual considerations. This model examines the direct and indirect effects between latent variables, allowing researchers to test specific hypotheses or theories about how the constructs relate to each other. It provides insights into the underlying processes or mechanisms that drive the relationships between variables [09]. The parameters in the structural model are estimated using regression analysis techniques or path analysis. To assess discriminant validity using the Fornell-Larcker criterion, calculate the AVE for each latent variable and the squared correlation (r^2) between each pair of latent variables. The AVE for a latent variable should be larger than the squared correlation between that latent variable and any other latent variable in the model to establish discriminant validity (see Table II). If the AVE is greater than the squared correlation, it suggests that the latent variables are distinct and have discriminant validity.

TABLE II. DISCRIMINANT VALIDITY

Scale	KNW	BLF	TRST	WLN	ACP	SE
Knowledge	0.669					
Beliefs	0.548	0.521				
Trust	0.543	0.408	0.326			
Willingness	0.659	0.621	0.405	0.490		
Acceptance of OBE	0.748	0.812	0.814	0.568	0.625	
Sustainable Education	0.625	0.748	0.725	0.628	0.525	0.677

To assess discriminant validity using the HTMT criterion, compare the HTMT ratio to a threshold value. Typically, a HTMT ratio less than 0.85 indicates discriminant validity, suggesting that the latent variables are sufficiently distinct. HTMT analysis is a more relevant statistical method for evaluating both discriminant and convergent validity (see Table III).

TABLE III. HTMT CRITERION

Scale	KNW	BLF	TRST	WLN	ACP	SE
Knowledge	0.829					
Beliefs	0.725	0.712				
Trust	0.655	0.518	0.528			
Willingness	0.780	0.714	0.628	0.528		

Acceptance of OBE	0.807	0.730	0.789	0.668	0.722	
Sustainable Education	0.799	0.628	0.780	0.728	0.524	0.805

TABLE IV. HYPOTHESES TESTING

Scale	Sam. X	SD	T-stat	Sig
Knowledge → Acceptance of OBE	0.574	0.107	5.461	0.001
Beliefs → Acceptance of OBE	0.406	0.107	3.721	0.000
Trust → Acceptance of OBE	0.529	0.215	4.215	0.015
Willingness → Acceptance of OBE	0.169	0.134	1.498	0.001
Acceptance of OBE → Sustainable Education	0.245	0.249	3.214	0.003

The proposed model (see Table IV) was approved because the p-value was less than 0.05. (t.stat=5.461 p-value=0.001) indicates the substantial correlation between knowledge and acceptance of OBE. There is also a significant association between beliefs and acceptance of OBE (t.stat=3.721, p-value=0.00), trust and acceptance of OBE (t.stat=4.215, p-value=0.00), willingness and acceptance of OBE-learning (t.stat=3.721, p-value=0.00). Eventually, acceptance is a mediator between proposed factors and sustainable education (t.stat=3.721, p-value=0.00). The path coefficient of SEM conceptual framework for SE-OBE was also deemed fit to the model (see Figure 1). To navigate these complexities, it is imperative to consider India's unique cultural and contextual nuances and foster collaboration among educators, policymakers, and communities to advance OBE for sustainable education effectively. This result has collaborated with earlier work [05-08] and [11–13].

VI. CONCLUSION

In the purview of NEP-2020, OBE implementation in India has much potential in the future. To successfully deploy OBE, the drawbacks—which include standardized examinations, infrastructure issues, faculty training requirements, and societal expectations—need to be addressed. However, the future potential of OBE in India has some encouraging ramifications. OBE may respond to the requirements and interests of each student by having a flexible curriculum, resulting in more individualized and comprehensive education. Focusing on skill-based, value-added, ability enhancement courses gives students the competencies they need for the next century, improving their employability and preparing them for the changing work market. The continual improvement of OBE practices is ensured by data-driven assessment and feedback mechanisms. The expansion of access to high-quality education across the nation is made possible by technological integration, which opens up chances for online learning, digital tools, and personalized teaching. Education institutions, educators, students, businesses, decision-makers, and society must actively work together and make the necessary reforms to reach its full potential for the OBE initiative by NEP-2020 in India. This entails supplying faculties with training, improving the physical environment, changing the evaluation procedures, encouraging business and academic

collaborations, and putting supportive laws into place. By doing this, India can create a system of education that fosters talented and adaptable people, promotes economic progress, and meets the demands of a world that is changing quickly.

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